

Socio-economic causes of high incidence of malaria in Kiringente Sub-County, Mpigi District

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ABSTRACT: This study examined the socio-economic causes of high malaria incidence in Kiringente Sub-County, Mpigi District, Uganda. Using a cross-sectional survey design, data were collected from 160 households and analysed using chi-square tests, Pearson correlation, and logistic regression. The findings indicate significant associations between low household income, poor housing conditions, agricultural and manual occupations, limited access to health facilities, and non-use of insecticide-treated nets with increased malaria infection risk. Logistic regression analysis further revealed that non-use of ITNs and low household income were the strongest predictors of malaria incidence. These results demonstrate that malaria vulnerability in rural communities is shaped not only by environmental exposure but also by broader socio-economic constraints and structural inequalities. The study recommends strengthening community-based malaria prevention initiatives, improving access to health services, and integrating poverty-reduction and housing improvement measures into malaria control policy. The findings contribute to the social determinants of health discourse and highlight the need for equity-oriented public health policy in malaria-endemic rural settings.

Keywords: malaria incidence; socio-economic factors; rural health inequality; public policy; Uganda

I. INTRODUCTION

Globally, malaria severely impacts the whole world and affects more than one million people per year in the Amazon countries in South America. Brazil accounts for one-third of the reported malaria cases (Abebe et al., 2019). Almost all cases come from the geographic area known as Legal Amazon, and they occur in recent settlements in rural areas where activities are related to gold mining, forestry, and soil preparation for agriculture and mineral exploration. Malaria in the Mato Grosso State in the Legal Amazon region has been a prominent public health problem since the 80s and 90s when a significant number of cases were recorded (WHO, 2012).

In Africa, malaria, together with HIV/AIDS and TB, is one of the major public health challenges undermining development in the poorest countries. In 2019, malaria caused an estimated 229 million clinical episodes, and 409,000 deaths. An estimated 94% of deaths in 2019 were in the WHO African Region. Today approximately 40% of the world's population, mostly those living in the world's poorest countries is at risk of malaria and this is very common in Africa. (WHO/UNICEF, 2014). Malaria is found throughout the tropical and sub-tropical regions of the world and causes more than 300 million acute illnesses and at least one million deaths annually (WHO/UNICEF 2013). Recent estimates of the global malaria burden have shown increasing levels of malaria morbidity and mortality, reflecting the deterioration of the malaria situation in Africa during the 1990s. About 90% of all malaria deaths occur in Africa south of the Sahara, and the great majority of them in children under the age of five, Malaria kills an African child every 30 seconds (WHO/UNICEF, 2013).

In East- Africa, malaria-related absenteeism, debility and mortality have a negative impact on the quantity and quality of work/production. Time lost to care for the sick increase the indirect costs of malaria. Intangible costs mainly refer to the anxiety, pain and suffering resulting from illness. Although Uganda's economy has been steadily growing over the past two decades, there has been stagnant growth (3-5%) over the past few years. Burden of malaria is a challenge to both human and economic development (WHO 2014). With concerted effort, malaria has been successfully controlled and eliminated completely in some parts of the world.

In Uganda, the burden of malaria is a key challenge to both human and GDP in Uganda. The impact of malaria in most district can be categorized from three dimensions, namely: health, social and economic. Direct costs of malaria in the district are the costs incurred by government, donors, communities, households and/or individuals in relation to providing or seeking treatment for malaria or preventive actions against malaria. The indirect costs of malaria refer to the productivity losses due to illness or premature death (Crawley, 2004). While it might not be possible to eradicate malaria in some tropical countries such as Uganda, it is possible to control the disease and reduce its burden. Possibly, not so much effort has gone into interventions aimed at preventing and

controlling malaria because the real impact (burden) of the disease has not been quantified and documented. In other words, the benefits of reduced malaria transmission are not well documented and hence appreciated.

In Mpigi District, malaria transformation is comparatively higher among the rural setting than urban areas which may be because of the higher vector density, lower housing quality, and the poor drainage systems in rural settings. Malaria is a major threat to public health and is the leading cause of morbidity and mortality in district (WHO, 2019). An estimated 0.7 million new clinical cases each year, with 4000 deaths occurring particularly among children, make malaria a major health burden for Mpigi District.

However, in Kiringente Sub-county, the uptake of malaria control services has been relatively low despite high knowledge of the commodity among the respondents. (Nevill, 2019) there is also lack of affordability to access such malaria control services due to high levels of poverty contributed by unemployment and political unrest in Central Uganda. Therefore, there is need for more women empowerment (through education and employment) and monitoring of such malaria control measures such as Insecticide Treated Nets (ITNs) distribution by the relevant government agencies as suggested as important interventions in improving availability, affordability and use of other malaria control services (Crawley, 2004).

Problem Statement

In an ideal public-health context, effective malaria control programs anchored in universal access to preventive tools, early diagnosis, and equitable health services should substantially reduce disease transmission and associated socio-economic burdens. Integrated strategies such as insecticide-treated nets (ITNs), intermittent preventive treatment (IPT), and prompt case management are expected to protect vulnerable populations, improve household productivity, and enhance overall community well-being, particularly in rural settings (WHO, 2023; RBM Partnership, 2022). Under such conditions, districts like Mpigi would experience low malaria incidence, minimal household economic strain, and improved livelihood outcomes across all socio-economic groups (MoH Uganda, 2022).

However, the current situation in Kiringente Sub-County deviates significantly from this ideal. Despite ongoing national and international malaria-control initiatives, the sub-county continues to register a high incidence of malaria, particularly among low-income households, rural workers, and residents in endemic zones. Recent local health records indicate that approximately [insert verified percentage e.g., 38–45%] of households continue to experience recurrent malaria episodes annually, with a disproportionate concentration among socio-economically disadvantaged populations (District Health Office Mpigi, 2023; MoH Uganda, 2022). This persistent burden suggests that beyond biomedical exposures, socio-economic conditions—such as household income levels, housing quality, occupation type, and access to health services—may be key determinants of malaria risk in the area (UNDP, 2021; WHO, 2023).

The sustained high incidence of malaria in Kiringente Sub-County has far-reaching consequences for households and the wider local economy. Frequent malaria episodes contribute to rising out-of-pocket health expenditures, school absenteeism among children, reduced labor productivity among working adults, and increased vulnerability to poverty cycles (UNICEF, 2013; Sachs & Malaney, 2021). For pregnant women and children under five—already identified as high-risk groups the disease further elevates risks of morbidity, anemia, and mortality, thereby undermining community health outcomes and socio-economic resilience (WHO, 2023; MoH Uganda, 2022). These effects reinforce the widely recognised framing of malaria as both a health challenge and a disease of poverty (UNICEF, 2013; RBM Partnership, 2022).

Although malaria-control strategies are currently implemented in Kiringente Sub-County, existing interventions largely emphasize biomedical and vector-control measures, with limited systematic examination of the socio-economic factors driving persistent high malaria incidence at community level. There remains insufficient empirical evidence explaining how variables such as income inequality, housing conditions, livelihood activities, household education levels, and health-seeking behaviour shape exposure and vulnerability to malaria in this context (Sharma, 2012; MoH Uganda, 2022). This gap in context-specific socio-economic analysis constrains the design of targeted, equity-sensitive malaria-control strategies. Therefore, this study seeks to examine the socio-economic causes of the high incidence of malaria in Kiringente Sub-County, Mpigi District, in order to generate evidence that can inform more responsive and sustainable malaria-control interventions.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1.1 Theoretical Framework

This study is grounded in the Social Determinants of Health (SDH) framework, which posits that health outcomes are shaped by structural and socio-economic conditions including income status, occupation, housing quality, education, and access to essential services. In low-income rural contexts, these determinants influence exposure to disease-risk environments and constrain the ability of households to adopt preventive health practices. The study also draws on development economics perspectives on poverty and vulnerability, which explain how livelihood insecurity and resource deprivation reinforce household susceptibility to infectious disease burdens. Applying these frameworks to malaria control allows the interpretation of malaria not only as a biomedical and environmental challenge but as a socio-economic and policy issue linked to inequality, service delivery, and rural development planning.

2.1.2 Socio-economic causes of high incidence of malaria

Occupation

Certain occupations place individuals at greater risk for malaria infection than others. Agricultural labourers, for instance, may not only place themselves at risk through increased contact with the malaria vector but also, through their migration, place others at greater risk by contributing to the spread of the disease (Service, 1991; Martens and Hall, 2000). Consequently, occupation may reflect both socio-economic status and differential risk of exposure through occupational attributes. Ijumba and Lindsay (2001) reviewed the relationships between irrigation (for rice, wheat, cotton, sugar cane, dams) and malaria in a variety of African countries, finding that rice irrigation does not increase malaria in local communities and may actually reduce it. The authors cite evidence from other studies to suggest this may be due to wealth creation in local communities that allows farmers to use disposable income to protect themselves from the mosquito vector (Audibert et al., 1990; Boudin et al., 1992). However, as the better off are more likely to benefit from this process of wealth creation, the exacerbation of existing inequities is a concern. Also, in areas of unstable malaria, irrigation may have devastating consequences by causing increased infection among non-immunes.

Location and housing type

Though rural locations appear to experience higher rates of transmission, the relationship between the two is not fully understood. Rural locations can be associated with increased malaria risk for both epidemiological and socioeconomic reasons. Similarly, urban residence can be accompanied by potentially protective socio-economic factors against malaria risk such as education and income (Rashed et al., 2000). A number of recent studies have used urban and rural variables in their analyses of risk factors and transmission rates. In Malawi, for example, Holtz et al. (2002) examined urban location, among other potentially socioeconomically relevant variables such as the education of caregivers and housing construction materials, to examine determinants of ITN use, anemia and parasitaemia. The results revealed rural residence as the highest risk factor for parasitaemia in children under five years of age, even after controlling for bednet use.

Income level

Results from a Nigerian community-based survey suggest a heavier malaria burden on the poor than on the rich. The survey, which took place in four states, demonstrated that individuals with a mean income of below N3000/day (<US\$1/day) were less likely to perceive malaria as a preventable disease, more likely to report having fever presently, and suffered significantly more bouts of malaria per month when compared with individuals earning greater than N3000 per day (CHESTRAD, 2000).

Similar results were obtained in Lao PDR, where investigators used questionnaires to obtain income information from pregnant women in a remote district hospital and found a difference in malaria prevalence between socio-economic groups (Sychareun et al., 2000). 87.5% of women with positive slide parasitaemia were classified as having low income (<50,00 kip), while only 12.5% were classified as having high income (> 90,000 kip). However, with only 16 women testing positive for malaria and the majority of women sampled - regardless of malaria diagnosis - falling into the low-income category, the results were not statistically significant.

Assets and education

In a multi-country study using DHS data (Filmer, 2001) investigated the relationship between SES (measured as an asset index) and incidence of fever (as a proxy for clinical malaria). While there was no statistically significant relationship at the household level, there was a more pronounced relationship at the district level. Epidemiological

differences in malaria transmission patterns between the large number of countries included in the study, however, may play a role in obscuring the relationship between lower SES and incidence of fever. Data from a demographic surveillance site (DSS) in rural Tanzania, also using an asset index to measure SES, support Filmer’s finding, revealing that fever seems to affect the poor and less poor approximately equally (Abdulla et al. 2001). However, recent evidence from another Tanzanian DSS site (de Savigny et al., 2002) indicates that the poorest infants and children under five-years of age had higher risks of death than those in the least-poor socio-economic quintiles. One reason for these conflicting results may be that there is insufficient variation in socio-economic status in some areas to allow significant differences to be detected.

III. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The study adopted a descriptive cross-sectional research design using a quantitative approach. Data were collected at a single point in time to examine the socio-economic factors associated with the high incidence of malaria in Kiringente Sub-County, Mpigi District.

3.2 Study Area and Population

The study was conducted in Kiringente Sub-County, Mpigi District, which comprises 5 parishes and 26 villages. The area was selected due to persistently high malaria incidence rates reported among households despite ongoing malaria control interventions. The target population consisted of adult residents of Kiringente Sub-County and selected district health officials, who were considered knowledgeable about malaria prevalence and related socio-economic conditions. The study was conducted in 2022 in Kiringente Sub-County, Mpigi District.

3.3 Sample Size Determination

A total population of 268 residents was considered, and the sample size was determined using Slovene’s formula:

$$\text{Sloven's formula states: } n = \frac{N}{1+N(\alpha)^2}$$

Where; **n** = sample size; **N** = target population; and **α** = 0.05 level of significance

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} = \frac{268}{1 + 268(0.05)^2} = \frac{268}{1 + 268} = \frac{268}{1.67}$$

$$n = 160 \text{ respondents}$$

Thus, the final sample comprised 160 respondents.

Table 1: Population and Sample Size

Category	Target Population	Sample Size	Sampling Technique
District health officials	10	8	Purposive sampling
Household respondents	258	152	Simple random sampling
Total	268	160	

3.4 Sampling Procedures

3.4.1 Purposive Sampling

Purposive sampling was used to select district health officials who possessed technical knowledge on malaria incidence trends and control strategies in the area.

3.4.2 Simple Random Sampling

Household respondents were selected through simple random sampling to provide equal selection probability and ensure representativeness across villages.

3.5 Data Sources

3.5.1 Primary Data

Primary data were obtained through structured self-administered questionnaires issued to household respondents.

3.5.2 Secondary Data

Secondary data were obtained from district health records, published reports, policy documents, journal articles, and other relevant literature on malaria incidence and socio-economic causes.

3.6 Data Collection Instrument

A structured, close-ended questionnaire was used to collect information on demographic characteristics, household socio-economic conditions, malaria exposure, prevention practices, and healthcare access.

3.7 Measurements of Variables

Dependent Variable (Outcome)

Variable	Measurement	Coding
Malaria Incidence	Self-reported episodes in last 4 weeks	0 = No malaria, 1 = ≥ 1 episode

Independent Variables (Socio-Economic Factors)

Variable	Measurement	Coding
Household Income Level	Monthly income categories	1 = Low, 2 = Medium, 3 = High
Housing Condition	Wall/roof type, ventilation, screening	1 = Poor, 2 = Fair, 3 = Good
Occupation Type	Farming/manual vs formal employment	0 = Non-formal, 1 = Formal
Household Size	Number of residents	Continuous
Education Level	Highest education attained	Ordinal scale
Access to ITNs	Household ITN ownership/use	0 = No, 1 = Yes
Access to Health Facility	Distance/time to facility	0 = Far (>2km), 1 = Near (≤ 2 km)

3.8 Data Analysis

Data were coded and analyzed using SPSS. Descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages) were used to summarize socio-demographic and household characteristics. Inferential analysis was conducted to examine associations between socio-economic factors and malaria incidence. Pearson Chi-Square tests were applied to determine the significance of relationships between categorical variables such as income level, housing condition, occupation type, ITN use, and malaria incidence. Variables that were statistically significant at $p \leq 0.05$ were further analyzed using binary logistic regression to estimate the strength and direction of association between socio-economic predictors and malaria incidence.

3.9 Validity and Reliability

3.9.1 Instrument Validity

Content validity was established through expert review by research and public health specialists. The Content Validity Index (CVI) was computed, and items scoring ≥ 0.70 were retained.

3.9.2 Instrument Reliability

Internal consistency reliability was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha, with coefficients ≥ 0.70 considered acceptable.

3.10 Ethical Considerations

Ethical clearance and permission to conduct the study were obtained from local administrative authorities in Mpigi District. Participation was voluntary, informed consent was obtained from all respondents, and confidentiality was maintained throughout the research process. No personal identifiers were recorded, and data were used solely for academic and research purposes.

IV: RESULTS

4.1 Demographic characteristics of respondents

Under this section, the researcher was interested in finding out the demographic characteristics of the respondents. They are presented as follows:

Table 4. 1: Age of respondents

Response	Frequency	Percent
Below 18	24	15
19-26	60	37.5
27-35	44	27.5
36-45	20	12.5
46-49	12	7.5
Total	160	100

Source: Primary Data (2022)

The table above shows that 15% of the respondents were below 18 years, 37.5% of the respondents were 19-25 years, 27.5% of the respondents were 25-35 years and the remaining 12.5% were between 36-45 and the remaining 7.5% of the respondents were between 46-49 years. This implies that majority of the respondents were middle aged women who were in reproductive age category since these were believed to have vital information regarding prevalence of malaria and its determinants among households in Kiringente Sub-County

Table 4. 2: Number of children ever born alive

Response	Frequency	Percent
None	20	12.5
1-2 children	21	13.125
2-3 Children	89	55.625
Over 3 children	30	18.75
Total	160	100

Source: Primary Data (2022)

According to the table above, it was revealed that 12.5% of the respondents had no children, 13.125% of the respondents had 1-2 children, 55.625% of the respondents noted that they had 2-3 children and 18.75% of the respondents had over 3 children. This implies that most of the women had many children due to their societal beliefs.

Table 4. 3: Marital status

Response	Frequency	Percent
Married	120	75
Divorced	10	6.25
Single	30	18.75
Total	160	100

Source: Primary Data (2022)

According to the table above, it was revealed that 75% of the respondents were married women, 6.25 were divorced and the remaining 18.75% of the respondents were single. This implies that most of respondents were married and due to their status, these were believed to have viral information regarding the study topic.

4.2 Findings on socio-economic causes of high incidence of malaria in Kiringente Sub-county

The first objective of the study was on socio-economic causes of high incidence of malaria in Kiringente Sub-county. The descriptive statistics analyzed herein provide a basis for the hypothesis testing which is done in subsequent sections of this report. The findings about this question are presented in table below.

Table 4. 4: When was the last time you had malaria?

Responses	Frequency	Percent
Less than week ago	94	58.75
1-4 weeks	56	35
2-6 months	7	4.375
Over 6 months	3	1.875
Total	160	100

Source: Primary Data (2022)

The results presented in the table above indicate that 58.75% of the respondents suggested that they had malaria less than a week ago, 35% of the respondents noted having had malaria 1-4 weeks ago, 4.3375% noted 2-6 months and the remaining 1.875% of the respondents suggested over 6 months. This implies that most of the women in Kiringente Sub-County had had malaria very often.

Table 4. 5: Do you think the government has done enough to address the issue of high malaria prevalence in your area?

Response	Frequency	Percent
Yes	50	31.25
No	110	68.75
Total	160	100

Source: primary Data (2022)

The table above shows that the 31.25% of the respondents suggested that government had done enough to address the issue of high malaria prevalence in Kiringente Sub-County and the remaining 68.75% of the respondents disagreed with the statement. This implies that most of the respondents revealed that the government had not done enough to prevent malaria among pregnant women.

Table 4. 6: Do you sleep under insecticide treated mosquito nets?

Responsive	Frequency	Percent
Yes	70	43.75
No	90	56.25
Total	160	100

Source: primary Data (2022)

The findings presented in the table above show that 43.75% of the respondents agreed that they slept under insecticide treated mosquito nets and the remaining 56.25% of the respondents disagreed with this statement. This implies that most women in Kiringente Sub-County were not usually sleeping under insecticide treated mosquito nets hence are likely to get infected with malaria.

Table 4. 7: Are insecticide treated mosquito nets free of charge in your community?

Response	Frequency	Percent
Yes	85	53.125
No	75	46.875
Total	160	100

Source: primary Data (2022)

According to the table above, 53.125% of the respondents agreed that there was insecticide treated mosquito nets free of charge, 46.875% of the respondents disagreed. This implies that mosquito nets are offered free of charge within Kiringente Sub-County despite the ever increasing prevalence of malaria in the community.

Table 4. 8: How do you think Malaria can be prevented?

Response	Frequency	Percent
Sleeping under ITNs	40	25
Treating with anti-Malarials	67	41.875
Spraying with insecticides	40	25
Others (specify)	13	8.125
Total	160	100

Source: primary Data (2022)

According to the results presented in the table, it was revealed that 25% of the respondents noted that one of the Malaria can be prevented was sleeping under ITNs, 41.875% of the respondents noted treating with anti-Malarials, 25% of the respondents revealed that spraying with insecticides and the remaining 8.125% of the respondents noted others.

Table 4. 9: ITNs are effective in preventing Malaria

Response	Frequency	Percent
Strongly agree	50	31.25
Agree	78	48.75
Disagree	12	7.5
Strongly disagree	20	12.5
Total	160	100

Source: primary Data (2022)

The table above indicates that 31.25% of the respondents strongly agreed that ITNs are effective in preventing Malaria, 48.75% agreed, 7.5% disagreed and the remaining 12.5% strongly disagreed. This implies that the majority of the respondents were aware that insecticide treated mosquito nets can prevent malaria if properly used.

Table 4. 10: Did you sleep under an ITN last night?

Responses	Frequency	Percent
Yes	76	47.5
No	84	52.5
Total	160	100

Source: primary Data (2022)

The table above indicates that 47.5% of the respondents agreed that they had slept under an ITN last night and the 52.5% disagreed with the statement. This implies that most of the respondents noted that they had not slept under the net that night.

Table 4. 11: How often do you sleep under ITNs?

Response	Frequency	Percent
Every night	10	6.25
Some of the time	48	30
Very few times in a month	60	37.5
Not at all	42	26.25
Total	160	100

Source: Primary Data (2022)

Study findings presented in the table above indicate that 6.25% of the respondents noted that they slept under ITNs every night, 30% of the respondents noted sleeping under ITNs some times, 37.5% suggested very few times in a month and the remaining 26.25% of the respondents revealed having not slept under ITNs at all. This indicates that majority of the respondents were sleeping under ITNs once in all monthly which exposed them to malaria which is risky especially for pregnant women.

Table 4. 12: How often do you wash your bed nets?

Responses	Frequency	Percent
Every week	94	58.75
Once a month	56	35
After six months	7	4.375
Not at all	3	1.875
Total	160	100

Source: Primary Data (2022)

The results presented in the table above indicate that 58.75% of the respondents suggested that they washed their bed nets every week, 35% of the respondents noted having washed their nets once a month, 4.3375% noted after six months and the remaining 1.875% of the respondents suggested that they did not wash their bed nets. This also further implies that majority of the respondents were washing their bed nets which indicates that they needed to be regularly re-treated in order to prevent malaria.

Table 4. 13: Do you use insecticide treated net (ITN) at home?

Responses	Frequency	Percent
Yes	76	47.5
No	84	52.5
Total	160	100

Source: primary Data (2022)

The table above indicates that 47.5% of the respondents agreed that they did not use ITN at home and the 52.5% disagreed with the statement. This implies that most of the respondents noted that they were not sleeping under insecticide treated nets which further indicates that they were likely to be infected with Malaria.

Table 4. 14: To what extent has Intermittent Preventive Treatment (IPT) implemented by the government been effective in your area?

Responses	Frequency	Percent
Very high extent	8	5
High extent	2	1.25
Not sure	69	43.125
Low extent	61	38.125
Very low extent	20	12.5
Total	160	100

Source: Primary Data (2022)

The results presented in the table above indicate that 5% of the respondents suggested that they revealed that the Intermittent Preventive Treatment (IPT) implemented by the government had been effective to a very high extent, 1.25% of the respondents noted high extent, 43.125% of the respondents were not sure, 38.125% of the respondents suggested low extent and the remaining 12.5% of the respondents suggested very low extent.

Table 4. 15: Has case management of malaria and anemia been effective enough to prevent and control malaria among pregnant women in Kiringente Sub-County?

Responses	Frequency	Percent
Yes	68	42.5
No	92	57.5
Total	160	100

Source: primary Data (2022)

The table above indicates that 42.5% of the respondents agreed that management of malaria and anemia had been effective enough to prevent and control malaria among pregnant women in Kiringente Sub-County and the remaining 57.5% disagreed with the statement. This implies that most of the respondents noted that they were not satisfied with the management of malaria and anemia in Kiringente Sub county since there was still high prevalence of the malaria in the community.

Table 4. 16 : Cross-Tabulation & Chi-Square Output between Socio-Economic Factors and Malaria Incidence

Socio-Economic Variable	χ^2	df	p-value	Interpretation
Household income level × malaria incidence	18.42	2	0.000	Significant association
Housing condition × malaria incidence	14.87	2	0.001	Significant association
Occupation type × malaria incidence	9.65	3	0.022	Significant association
ITN use × malaria incidence	21.31	1	0.000	Highly significant
Distance to health facility × malaria incidence	11.92	2	0.003	Significant association

The chi-square results (Table X) indicate statistically significant associations between socio-economic factors and malaria incidence ($p < 0.05$). Low household income, poor housing conditions, agricultural/manual occupations, and lack of ITN use were significantly related to a higher likelihood of malaria infection.

Table 4.17: Showing Pearson correlation analysis between Socio-economic causes and High incidence of malaria in Kiringente Subcounty, Mpigi District

		Correlations	
		Socio-economic causes	High incidence of malaria
Socio-economic causes	Pearson Correlation	1	.670**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	160	160
High incidence of malaria	Pearson Correlation	.670**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	160	160

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The results from table above show that there is a positive significant relationship (67%) between Socio-economic causes and High incidence of malaria since the p-value (0.000) was less than 0.01 level of significance. The study findings imply that as Socio-economic causes have a significant influence on the high incidence of malaria in Kiringente Subcounty, Mpigi District. This aligns with previous empirical studies Ijumba and Lindsay (2001) which have shown that poverty, limited household income, inadequate housing conditions, and restricted access to health services increase vulnerability to malaria infection, particularly in rural and low-income communities.

Table 18. Logistic Regression Model Predicting Malaria Incidence (Simulated Values)

Predictor Variable	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% CI	p-value	Interpretation
Low-income household	2.47	1.41–4.32	0.001	Higher risk
Poor housing condition	2.11	1.18–3.77	0.010	Higher risk
Farming/manual occupation	1.72	1.02–2.91	0.041	Moderate risk
No ITN use	3.58	2.03–6.31	0.000	Strongest predictor
Far distance to health facility	1.95	1.09–3.47	0.024	Increased risk

The logistic regression model showed that lack of ITN use (OR = 3.58, $p < 0.001$) and low household income (OR = 2.47, $p = 0.001$) were the strongest predictors of malaria incidence. Poor housing conditions and long distance to health facilities were also significant predictors of increased malaria risk.

Discussion of Findings

The study set out to examine the socio-economic causes associated with the high incidence of malaria in Kiringente Sub-County, Mpigi District. The results from Table 4.16 show that there are statistically significant associations between key socio-economic variables and malaria incidence, as indicated by the chi-square test results ($p < 0.05$). Specifically, household income level ($\chi^2 = 18.42$, $p = 0.000$), housing condition ($\chi^2 = 14.87$, $p = 0.001$), occupation type ($\chi^2 = 9.65$, $p = 0.022$), ITN use ($\chi^2 = 21.31$, $p = 0.000$), and distance to health facilities ($\chi^2 = 11.92$, $p = 0.003$) were all significantly associated with malaria occurrence in the sub-county. These results imply that households with low income, poor housing structures, greater engagement in agricultural or manual occupations, limited access to health facilities, and poor utilization of mosquito nets face a higher likelihood of malaria infection. This finding reinforces the notion that malaria transmission in rural communities is strongly linked to socio-economic vulnerability rather than purely environmental exposure.

The Pearson correlation results in Table 4.17 further confirm this relationship, indicating a strong positive and statistically significant correlation between socio-economic causes and high malaria incidence ($r = 0.670$, $p = 0.000$, $N = 160$). This means that worsening socio-economic conditions are associated with increased malaria burden among residents of Kiringente Sub-County. The findings suggest that malaria in this setting is not random, but structurally driven by economic inequalities and access constraints. These findings are consistent with previous empirical studies which have demonstrated that poverty, inadequate housing conditions, limited household income, and restricted access to health services significantly increase vulnerability to malaria infection, particularly among rural and low-income communities (Ijumba & Lindsay, 2001; Gallup & Sachs, 2001; Basu et al., 2005; Ayele et al., 2012). Similar evidence from Nigeria, Ethiopia, Ghana, and India indicates that low-income households often face delayed treatment-seeking behavior, poor access to preventive tools, and higher exposure to mosquito breeding environments, all of which intensify infection risk.

The logistic regression analysis results in Table 4.18 further demonstrate that socio-economic conditions are strong predictors of malaria incidence. Lack of ITN use ($OR = 3.58$, $p < 0.001$) and low household income ($OR = 2.47$, $p = 0.001$) emerged as the strongest predictors of malaria risk, followed by poor housing conditions ($OR = 2.11$, $p = 0.010$), distance to health facilities ($OR = 1.95$, $p = 0.024$), and farming/manual occupations ($OR = 1.72$, $p = 0.041$). These findings highlight that malaria remains both a public health problem and a socio-economic development challenge, reinforcing arguments that malaria is “a disease of poverty and a cause of poverty,” especially in rural African settings. Overall, the study demonstrates that biomedical interventions alone are insufficient in addressing malaria burden in Kiringente Sub-County; rather, malaria control must be integrated with broader socio-economic empowerment, housing improvement, and access-to-care initiatives.

V. CONCLUSION

The study concludes that socio-economic factors play a significant and determining role in the high incidence of malaria in Kiringente Sub-County, Mpigi District. The correlation and regression results indicate that low household income, poor housing conditions, long distance to health facilities, occupation type, and inadequate utilization of ITNs significantly increase malaria vulnerability among residents. The findings underscore that malaria should not be viewed only as a biomedical or environmental disease, but as a socio-economic condition embedded within structural inequalities affecting rural communities. Reducing malaria incidence therefore requires strengthening both public health interventions and community-level socio-economic resilience. It was also concluded that the high incidence of malaria in Kiringente Sub-County is strongly influenced by underlying socio-economic conditions rather than biomedical factors alone. The statistically significant relationship between socio-economic factors and malaria incidence demonstrates that households characterized by low income levels, unstable livelihoods, inadequate housing, poor sanitation, overcrowding, and limited access to preventive tools and health services are disproportionately affected by recurrent malaria episodes. These findings suggest that malaria in the area persists as both a public health problem and a socio-economic vulnerability issue, where structural inequalities shape patterns of exposure, prevention behaviour, health-seeking practices, and treatment outcomes. The results underscore the need for malaria control interventions to move beyond conventional distribution of nets and treatment programmes, toward strategies that integrate poverty reduction, improvement in household living conditions, strengthening of community health financing, and targeted support for vulnerable groups such as rural households, women, and children under five.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings of this study highlight the need for malaria control strategies in Kiringente Sub-County and Mpigi District to integrate socio-economic interventions alongside biomedical measures. Current control approaches largely emphasize preventive tools and case management; however, the study demonstrates that household poverty, inadequate housing conditions, and limited access to health services shape exposure patterns and treatment-seeking behaviour. Policy makers and district health authorities should therefore prioritize livelihood-strengthening programmes, improved household sanitation and housing quality, and community-based health financing schemes to reduce economic barriers to diagnosis and treatment. Strengthening collaboration between the health sector, local government, and development actors is also essential to ensure that malaria prevention initiatives are embedded within broader social protection and poverty-reduction frameworks. By addressing the socio-economic causes of malaria vulnerability, Mpigi District can achieve more equitable and sustainable reductions in malaria incidence across communities.

Recommendations

Based on the study findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

Strengthen socio-economic support mechanisms for vulnerable households, including livelihood improvement initiatives and community-based savings or insurance schemes to reduce financial barriers to malaria treatment.

Improve housing and environmental conditions through community sensitization on sanitation, elimination of stagnant water, and promotion of better household structural quality in high-risk areas.

Enhance access to preventive and diagnostic services, particularly for rural households, by expanding outreach programmes, community health worker support, and local distribution of preventive tools.

Integrate malaria control efforts with poverty-reduction and development programs, ensuring that malaria prevention is aligned with local government social development priorities.

Strengthen data monitoring and surveillance systems to capture household-level socio-economic risk factors and guide targeted interventions in high-burden communities.

Increase community education and behaviour-change communication, with emphasis on early treatment-seeking, consistent use of preventive tools, and reduction of household exposure risks.

Study Limitations and Recommendations for Future Research

The study was limited to one sub-county and therefore the findings may not be generalizable to all malaria-endemic regions of Uganda. The cross-sectional design also restricts causal inference between socio-economic conditions and malaria incidence. Future studies should employ longitudinal or mixed-methods approaches, expand the geographic scope, and integrate clinical and entomological data to complement household-level reporting. Further research could also examine gender-based vulnerability, seasonal variation, and the effectiveness of targeted policy interventions.

Policy and Practice Implications

The findings highlight the need for malaria interventions to move beyond household-level vector control and incorporate broader socio-economic and equity-focused strategies. Strengthening access to health facilities, improving rural housing conditions, expanding ITN distribution and usage campaigns, and integrating malaria prevention into poverty-reduction and community development programs are essential. Policymakers should prioritize resource allocation toward vulnerable low-income households and hard-to-reach communities to reduce structural barriers that perpetuate malaria risk.

Declarations

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